

USAGE OF ENGLISH LITERATURE IN EFFECTIVE TEACHING AND LEARNING LANGUAGE IN ESL CLASSES

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Abstract. *The paper presents information about literary texts material usage as a tool for creating interesting and effective teaching and learning atmosphere in the ESL classroom, plus the appropriate ways for material selecting process.*

Keywords: *literature, the text, the reader, motivation, culture, writing skills, reading comprehension, cultural background.*

Introduction

The primary tool for teaching and learning a language is literature. Language excels in literature, which is a natural setting for it. Literature offered extra resources for translating, acquiring new words, and practicing grammar (Liaw 2001; cited in Khatib Hossein and Rahimi 2012: p.32).

Literature is a tool for language learning. Language acquisition is actually a process whose goals differ not just from nation to nation and culture to culture, but also from individual to person. In actuality, each student is free to choose whether or not the literature will be incorporated in any manner into the course curriculum or particular lesson plans. If this is the case, then teachers must choose which texts to include, how to utilize them, and what steps will be taken to help students study the texts and strengthen their language skills. The literature will be useful for teaching and learning the language if it is chosen with the needs, academic level, and age of the pupils in mind.

What is literature?

There are numerous definitions of literature that come from various perspectives. The method of H.L.B. Moody can be considered as the most general definition. Moody claimed that literature functions like an all-encompassing term that provides knowledge on every industry (Moody, 1971:1, referenced in Turker 1991: p. 299). Literature can thus be the best medium for expressing a particular subject because it is interested in all forms of written and spoken communication, such as literature for language learning, literature for childrearing, literature for communication, literature for construction, literature for medicine, literature for business, and literature for the author's style. A literary text should be viewed as an example of aesthetic communication, according to Sonia Zyngier (1994).

If we continue to define "Literature" in terms of language teaching, we discover a crucial definition. The efficient use of language under appropriate circumstances is what Alexander Baird defined as literature (Arthur Baird 1968:203, referenced in Turker 199: p-300). According to him, literary texts can be used to teach language because the language is appropriate for the settings in which the events are set. The use of language is the most significant of literature's functions, as seen by the definitions above. The approach is used by foreign language teachers in accordance with the syllabus and the level of the pupils. Because of this, literature has emerged as the most effective tool for language acquisition and teaching.

Literary texts as a tool for teaching English language

Reading literature, in accordance with Povey (1972), exposes kids to a sophisticated vocabulary and fresh, complicated grammar, expanding their use of language and linguistic expertise. Particularly in the context of EFL, McCay (1982) holds that the role relations are predetermined and the social context is taken into account while reading literary works, which can be used to raise students' awareness of the language's use. The empirical and motivational elements that literature offers, as well as their impact on pupils' reading abilities, are additional benefits of reading literature. If we think of reading as a dialogue between the reader and the text, then the reader must be prepared and motivated to read, and the literature can be seen as a means of ensuring motivation. Accomplishing reading goals will help you in school and at work. The literature also benefits kids by fostering their creativity and promoting tolerance for cultural differences.

The benefits of using the literature as a resource in EFL and ESL settings are outlined by Mayley (2001). 1. *Universality*: Literature exists in all known languages, and themes like love, death, separation, and nature are shared by all cultures. Similar literary conventions and genres are followed by literature all around the world.

2. Contrary to many other language learning tools, nontriviality simplifies texts or experiences; literature does not. *It provides authentic and authentic content.*

3. *Ideas*: personal significance. The events and things that are portrayed in the literature can either be imagined or experienced by the students, allowing them to make connections between them and their own life.

4. *Variety*: The literature covers a wide range of languages and subject matters. Students can choose from a wide variety of literary materials that are not monotonous.

5. *Interest*: Because literature approaches well-known subjects in an engrossing and fascinating manner, it has a natural appeal.

6. *The literary trademarks of economy and strength of suggestion.* It's the rebellious connotation that words and sentences evoke.

Ideas can be expressed in a few words in literature, which transcends what is spoken.

Ambiguousness: The text leaves room for several interpretations. The same book is rarely read by two people in exactly the same way. This variety of methods and readings makes it possible to have a sincere discussion and encourages involvement. Each learner can also be confident in the accuracy of their interpretations of a particular book.

There are three ways that literature can aid in language learning, according to Arthur (1968). First of all, compared to speech, literature uses a much larger word pool. The second is distinctive syntactic constructions that are exclusive to written English, particularly literature. Use of the passive voice, the recurrence of subordinate clauses, subordination inside subordination, and the inversion of stylistic order are a few examples. Students are helped by literature to understand various societies and cultures, which is the third advantage. The actions and occurrences of the characters follow the rules of a specific culture or community.

The use of the literature in ESL and EFL settings has two benefits, according to Oster (1989). When used in the classroom, literature "expands students' horizons and promotes critical thinking" (85). Reading literature encourages readers to explore plot points, characters, and interpretations, which enables kids to view the world from a variety of angles. Students pick up new reading techniques and come to terms with the fact that their peers have various perspectives. Oster lists the advantages of reading for writing skills, including fostering creativity, expanding

vocabulary and incorporating it into students' writing, and teaching students how to use figurative language to make writing more emotive.

Three advantages of using literature are provided by Hadaway, Wardell, and Young (2002). The language's contextualization comes first. When reading a work of literature, students gain knowledge of how language is used in various contexts. Another benefit of literature is the social and affective elements ingrained in the many literary styles, such as children's books, newspapers, and short stories. In this approach, literature can accommodate a range of learning styles and account for individual differences. The third benefit relates to the natural and meaningful use of language, which is accomplished through literary description and illustration.

According to Lazar (1993), literature can be used to foster chances for discussion, debate, and critical thinking.

Literary material selection:

The right choice of literary texts is essential to the efficient application of literature in ELT. uncomplicated stylistically in literary writings. Selecting subjects that kids can relate to is crucial. The struggle with a language and culture they are unfamiliar with is, of course, a common experience shared by the majority of ESL students. Therefore, any literature that addresses one of these subjects should be extremely pertinent to it.

(Extracted from McKAY 1982, pp. 531–532) In the creation of resource literature for linguistic development, text selection is a "decisive factor" (Masey, 2001: 184). cultural appreciation and personal enrichment. In addition, MCRAE (1997) asserts that "careful text selection is fundamental to the successful use of any kind of representative material" (1997: 49), and Collie and Slater (1994) contend that "each specific group of students, their needs, interests, cultural background, and language level" influence text choice (1994: 6). In his essay, Robert Hill (1995) provides examples of two sets of criteria. Lazar (1993: 52) discusses further standards. The following section contains the criteria that were combined from all of the sources indicated above:

- Student's cultural background;
- Student's language ability;
- Student's reading background;
- Student's age and degree of comprehension;
- Interesting accessible texts and text availability.

Conclusion

Literature serves as a source of fresh perspectives, information, vocabulary, and grammar practice. When students gain not only linguistic but also global and cultural knowledge, the process of learning and teaching a language can be improved with the aid of literature. Fiction books can be a valuable teaching tool if the literary selection is appropriate.

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